

Brownian Motion and Two Particle Collisions Leading to the MB Distribution

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The equation for Brownian motion is the Langevin equation which may be converted into a Fokker Planck equation: $d/dt f = -p/m df/dx + d/dp \{ [dV/dx + g(x,p)p/m] f \} + d/dp D(x,p) d/dp f$. This includes a friction term (the g term) and a Gaussian noise term (with D). For the stationary state $df/dt=0$, for D and g constant and $D/g = T$, one may obtain the MB distribution as a solution. This distribution, however, implies conservation of kinetic energy in a two particle collision. At first glance, however, Brownian motion does not seem to be related to conservation of energy. Yet somehow the stationary Brownian motion picture should be the same as an equilibrium gas picture in which two particles collide elastically.

The Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution may be derived in a variety of ways. A traditional way makes use of the Boltzmann transport equation which seems equivalent to two particle elastic collisions. In such a case, $f(p)f(p_1)=f(p_2)f(p_4)$. Taking the natural log of both sides yields a conservation equation which one may identify with kinetic energy conservation and thus obtain the MB distribution. In (1), however, p_2 is set equal to $p+dp$ and with conservation of energy: $p^2 + p_2^2 \approx p^2 + 2pdp + p_4^2$. This leads to the equation: $(df/dp 1/p) = \text{constant}$ which is essentially of the form of the stationary Brownian motion equation. Thus in this note, we try to examine the connection between the stationary Brownian motion case and an equilibrium MB gas.

Brownian Motion

The nonrelativistic Langevin equation describing Brownian motion is given in (2) as:

$$dp/dt = -dV/dx -gp + z(x,p,t) \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{Where Average}[z(x,p,t)] = 2D(x,p) \text{ delta function}(t-t') \quad ((2))$$

The authors write the corresponding Fokker-Planck equation describing the momentum and position distribution $f(x,p)$ as:

$$d/dt f = -p/m df/dx + d/dp \{ [dV/dx + g(x,p)p/m] f \} + d/dp D(x,p) d/dp f \quad ((3))$$

For the simplest case, consider $g(x,p)$ and $D(x,p)$ as constants. Then, one may obtain the MB distribution as a solution: $f(x,p) = B \exp(-1/T(.5/m p^2 + V))$ where $D/g=kT$.

One may note that $E = p^2/2m + V(x)$ and $f(E)$ so:

$-p/m df/dx + dV/dx d/dp f = 0$ and the stationary Brownian motion equation becomes:

$d/dp (g f p/m) = d/dp (D d/dp f)$ ((3b)) A solution of this is:

$g f p/m = D df/dp$ (g, D constants) with an $\exp(-a p^2)$ solution (i.e. MB) immediately present.

This result is presented frequently in the literature. What may seem a little surprising is that the MB distribution is also associated with an equilibrium system involving two particle elastic collisions. For example, p may collide with p_1 to produce p_2 and p_4 with kinetic energy conserved. Energy conservation at the two particle level is critical for the creation of an equilibrium situation. The MB distribution also preserves this idea of energy conservation because $f(p,x)=f(e)=\exp(-e/T)$ so that $f(p,x)f(p_1,x) = \exp(-1/T (e_1+e_2))$ which equals $f(p_2,x)f(p_4,x)$ for any p_2 and p_4 which conserve energy.

A question which arises is where does one see energy conservation in the Brownian motion case? Brownian motion starts with the idea of frictional energy loss and Gaussian random collisions. If this system moves into equilibrium, which the stationary solution seems to imply, why does the solution, i.e. the MB distribution, imply energy conservation for two particle collisions?

Maxwell-Boltzmann Two Particle Collision Equilibrium

The Boltzmann transport equation leads to a two particle elastic collision equation:

$f(p)f(p_1) = f(p_2)f(p_4)$ where both momentum and energy are conserved ((4))

One may consider ((4)) equivalent to an "and" probability equation in which specific two particle collisions become very important in the sense that there is energy conservation in each collision and time reversal balance. The general equilibrium does not, it seems, at first glance impose such a strict balance. It seems the equilibrium picture removes the sense of time flow which is linked to time reversal invariance. If ((4)) were not true, then a movie and its time reversed version would not be the same and one could see an overall change in time in the system, at least for the some specific reactions.

One may take the natural log of ((4)) to obtain a conservation equation. The natural entity to conserve is energy and so one immediately obtains the MB distribution.

This picture does not seem to have anything in common with Brownian motion, yet it seems there should be a link because the two scenarios both lead to the MB distribution.

In (1), a possible derivation of the MB distribution is presented which may provide an indication of a link between two particle collisions and Brownian motion, because it leads to the stationary Brownian motion equation.

In (1), the following two particle collision is considered:

$$f(p)f(p_1) = f(p+dp) f(p_4) \text{ where } p^2 + p_1^2 \text{ approx} = p^2 + 2pdp + p_4^2 \quad ((5))$$

This leads to: $p_4 \text{ approx} = p_1 (1 - p/p_1^2 df/dp_1)$ and:

$$0 = df/dp f(p_1) - f(p) p/p_1 df/dp_1 \quad ((6a)) \text{ or } df/dp = C f p \text{ where } C \text{ is a constant.} \quad ((6b))$$

((6b)), however, is of the same form as the Brownian motion stationary equation.

In particular, for the Brownian motion stationary equation ((3b)):

Friction is associated with $g p f$ and the Gaussian random motion with df/dp .

In the two particle equilibrium collision scenario with energy conservation:

The $p f$ term is associated with $f(p_4)$ and the Gaussian random motion with $f(p_1)$.

Thus, it seems a tiny collision of p moving it to $p+dp$ represents Gaussian random motion, while the change of p_1 into p_4 represents the friction term from the point of view of $f(p)$ in the collision: $p + p_1 \rightarrow p + dp + p_4$.

It is energy conservation at the collision level which allows for the MB solution. Furthermore, ((6a)) is a coupled equation, involving both $f(p)$ and $f(p_1)$. Thus, it seems the equation contains coupled Brownian motion, i.e. Brownian motion from the point of view of $f(p)$ and also from the point of view of $f(p_1)$. Thus, for $f(p) f(p_4) \rightarrow f(p_1) - p/p_1 dp df/dp_1$ seems to be linked to friction, but from the point of view of p_1 this would not be friction. Thus, the friction and Gaussian processes are intertwined. It seems to depend on which particle is being considered, thus the two particle collision picture seems to prevail, even in the Brownian motion stationary scenario with all particles in the collision participating. The Langevin equation and its counterpart, the Fokker-Planck seem to focus on one particle involved in the collisions and assign the others to friction and Gaussian noise.

Relativistic Scenario

As noted in (1), equations ((6a)) and ((6b)) may be applied to the relativistic case. The solution becomes the Maxwell-Juttner $\exp(-e/T)$ where $e = V(x) + \text{sqrt}(p^2 + m)$.

In (3), it is shown one may write a Fokker-Planck equation for the relativistic case, and that the stationary solution is the Maxwell-Juttner. Thus, the ideas above seem to hold for this relativistic scenario as well.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in this note we ask why the stationary solution of the Brownian process (the Fokker-Planck) equation which yields the MB distribution, carries with it the implicit idea of energy conservation? Energy conservation does not seem to be explicitly present in Brownian motion. Using the derivation of the MB distribution from (1) for two particle elastic collisions, one finds that the equation obtained ((6a)), ((6b)) match the Brownian motion stationary state equation. Thus, we attempt to argue that the two scenarios are linked and try to explain the frictional and Gaussian random terms.

References

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